

Research Article

Effects of Long Term Consumption of Cooked Black Eye Beans on Locomotor and Exploratory Behaviour in Mice

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Abstract

The effects of chronic consumption of cooked beans (Vigna unguiculata) diet on locomotor and exploratory behaviour were investigated. Thirty (30) CD1 mice weighing 15-30g were randomly assigned into three groups, viz; control, cooked beans diet (50% w/w), while another set of mice were placed on serotonin precursor (5-HTP) diet (0.2mg/50g w/w) respectively for thirty days. All the mice had access to clean drinking water ad libitum. Before the neurobehavioural parameters were assessed, the phytochemical analysis of the beans, LD₅₀ of the beans (Vigna unguiculata) and that of the serotonin precursor (5-HTP) were determined. Serotonin concentration was measured in the beans using gas chromatography analysis. The open field maze and light and dark transition box were employed for the evaluation of locomotor and exploratory behaviour. Daily food intake, water intake and body weight change were measured. The frequency of rearing in the open field was not significantly different in the cooked beans and serotonin precursor fed group compared to control. However, the frequency of line crosses, stretch attend posture and walling activity were decreased in the test group ($p < 0.05$; $p < 0.01$) compared to control. This indicates a decreased locomotor and exploratory behavior in the test group. There was also a significant ($p < 0.05$) decrease in the frequency of transition in the light/dark transition box for the cooked beans fed group when compared to the control. The administration of serotonin precursor diet (5-HTP) produced similar result as cooked beans, thus suggesting that serotonin may be involved in the action of beans on neurobehavioral parameters. Summarily, chronic consumption of cooked beans diet decreases locomotor and exploratory behaviour.

Keywords: Cooked beans, locomotion/exploration, open field, 5HTP and mice.

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Introduction

Bean offers a superb source of protein, carbohydrates, dietary fibre, minerals, vitamins and many phenolic compounds (Adeyeye, 1995). Nowadays, researchers are particularly interested in the high antioxidant activities observed in beans. Bean is a very nutritious food from many aspects and it is not surprising that nutritionists would characterize beans as a nearly perfect food (Shansudden and Elsayed, 1998; *Van der poel et al.*, 1990b). It has been reported that beans have anticarcinogenic, anti-mutagenic (Gref and Eaton, 1993; anti-inflammatory, anti-diabetic, hypoglycaemic, depurative, cardio-protective and antioxidant effects (Bennick *et al.*, 2008). It has also been reported that beans contain serotonin and its precursor 5-Hydroxytryptophan (5-HTP) (Portas *et al.*, 2000). Beans contain other chemical compounds including saponins, tannins, glycosides, flavonoids etc. Among the array of chemical constituents, notably, serotonin has neurobehavioural actions such as mood, memory, learning, and sleep (Brunton *et al.*, 2005). Serotonin has been shown to act (*Ceanorhabditis elegans*) as neurotransmitter to modulate behaviour in response to changing cues, acting on both neurons and muscles to affect egg laying, pharyngeal pumping, locomotion and learning (Daniel and Michael, 2007). Since beans contain neurotransmitters and chemicals that can potentially affect behavioural patterns, it may be worthwhile to find out whether long-term consumption of cooked beans diet can affect behaviour. This was of particular interest when we consider the challenges that confront human behaviour and how behavioural disorders still remain a global concern (Messman, 2005).

It is likely therefore, that some stable foods can affect behaviour. Beans constitute a major portion of the Nigerian local diet. It contains neurotransmitters, notably serotonin that has neurobehavioural actions as well as its precursor, 5-Hydroxytryptophan that also has similar actions. It is conceivable therefore that long term consumption of beans (cooked) diet can affect behaviour.

Materials and Methods

Experimental animals/grouping

Thirty (30) adult Swiss white mice weighing between 15-30g obtained from the disease-free stock of the animal house, Department of Physiology, University of Nigeria, Nsukka were used for this research work. The animals were randomly assigned into three (3) groups of ten (10) animals per group. Each mouse in a study group was individually housed in a plastic cage with iron gauze bottom grid and a wire screen top. The animal room was adequately ventilated, and kept at room temperature and humidity of $22\pm 3^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 40-70% respectively with 12 hour natural light-dark cycle.

The animals in the control group received normal rodent feed (rodent chow) only, while the test group received mixed feed of 50g of cooked beans (cooked in a pressure cooker for one hour) per every 50g of rodent chow making 1% of the beans diet for 30 days. This is sequel to the fact that the determined LD₅₀ for the intra-peritoneal administration of beans was 939.04mg/kg.

Experimental Design

The open field maze and light/dark transition box was used to access locomotor and exploratory behavior.

The open field test was used to provide measures of locomotion, exploration and anxiety (Walsh and Cummins, 1976). The experiment was performed in an enclosed laboratory to screen the animals from noise and provide dim light to avoid distraction. The animals were placed in the centre of the maze and allowed to explore the open field for 5 minutes. Before introducing each animal; the floor of the maze was cleaned using 70% ethyl alcohol in order to eliminate olfactory influences. The following behaviours were scored during the 5 minutes to assess locomotor and exploratory behaviours: line crossing, rearing, stretch attend posture, walling and freezing.

Also, the light and dark transition box is a test of locomotion and exploratory behaviour. Each mouse was picked up using a plastic bucket and placed in the centre division of the large compartment facing the floor. The mouse was allowed to explore the transition box for 5 minutes. Entering into the chamber is defined as the placement of all four paws into the chamber. During the period of 5 minutes, behaviour scored using a stop watch was frequency of transition.

Statistical Analysis

Data collected were expressed a Mean \pm SEM (standard error of mean), analysis of variance (ANOVA) and the student 't' test were used for analysis. "P" value less than 0.05, was considered statistically significant.

Results

Line Crossing

Figure 1.0 compares the frequency of line crosses in the three groups of mice. The horizontal locomotor behaviour following consumption of cooked beans, 5HTP and control diet was measured by the number of lines crossed by the animals (mice) within five minutes in the open field maze. The number of lines crossed by the mice were, 73.43 \pm 3.60 (control), 68.70 \pm 4.30 (cooked beans) and 53.43 \pm 2.00 (serotonin precursor).

The statistical analysis shown in the graph of figure 1, shows that the frequency of line crosses of the cooked beans and serotonin precursor fed mice was significantly lower ($P < 0.05$) compared to control. However, the frequency of line crosses of the serotonin precursor fed mice was significantly lower ($P < 0.01$) compared to the cooked beans group.

Rearing Frequency in the Open Field

Rearing and walling are forms of exploratory behaviours as well as vertical locomotor activity. The frequency of rearing in the open field for control mice beans were, 2.33 ± 0.94 (control), 4.13 ± 1.17 (cooked) beans and $12.57 \pm 0.48/5\text{mins}$ (serotonin precursor) respectively.

The graph in figure 2 shows that the frequency of rearing among the groups, when compared was significantly not different.

Walling Frequency

Figure 3 shows the frequency of walling in the three experimental groups. The values are: 27.60 ± 2.72 (control), 19.00 ± 2.93 (cooked beans) and 12.57 ± 2.38 (serotonin precursor) in 5 minutes. The frequency of walling in the group of mice fed cooked beans diet was significantly lower ($P < 0.05$) compared to control. However, the serotonin precursor diet fed mice was also significantly different at ($p < 0.01$) compared to control.

Freezing Frequency

Figure 4 compares the freezing frequency between the three experimental groups of mice respectively. The freezing frequency shown in figure 4 were, 0.90 ± 0.10 (control), 1.75 ± 0.20 (cooked) beans /5mins and $2.43 \pm 0.20/5\text{mins}$ (serotonin precursor).

The frequency of freezing among the group of mice fed cooked beans and 5HTP diet was significantly higher ($p < 0.001$) compared to control. However, the serotonin precursor group was statistically higher when compared to those of the cooked beans group.

Freezing Duration

The freezing duration shown in figure 5 were, 3.16 ± 1.51 (control), $10.26 \pm 3.00/5\text{mins}$ (cooked) beans and $32 \pm 1.41/5\text{mins}$ (serotonin precursor). The freezing duration in the group of mice fed cooked beans and serotonin precursor diet was also significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) compared to control. However, those fed with serotonin precursor diet were seen to be significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) than those of the cooked beans group.

Stretch Attend Posture (Sap) in the Open Field Maze.

Figure 6.0 compares the frequencies of the stretch attend posture (SAP) which is a measure of anxiety and exploration in the two experimental groups. The values are: 3.90 ± 0.12 (control), $3.13 \pm 0.13/5$ mins (cooked beans) and 2.86 ± 0.12 (serotonin precursor).

The frequency of stretch attend posture of the cooked beans and 5HTP group was significantly lower ($p < 0.05$) compared to control. However, those fed with the serotonin precursor diet was significantly lower compared to the cooked beans group.

Transition in the Light/Dark Box

The frequency of transition (that is the number of time the animals passes into the opposite compartment) between the four experimental groups is in figure 7. The values are: 16.70 ± 1.46 (control), $12.50 \pm 2.46/5$ mins (cooked beans) and 5.43 ± 0.65 (serotonin precursor).

The frequency of transition of the cooked beans group of mice was statistically lower ($p < 0.05$) compared to control. However, the serotonin precursor fed mice had a significantly lower ($p < 0.001$) frequency of transition compared to control and cooked beans group.

Fig 1: Frequency of line crossing in the different experimental groups during the open field test. Values are expressed as are expressed as mean \pm SEM, $n = 10$, * $p < 0.05$ vs. control; a = $p < 0.01$ vs. cooked beans.

Fig 2: Frequency of rearing in the different experimental group in the open field test. Values are expressed as mean \pm SEM, n = 10.

Fig 3: Walling frequencies in the different experimental groups during the open field test. Values are expressed as mean \pm SEM, n = 10, *p<0.05 vs. control; **p<0.01 vs. Control.

Fig 4: Frequency of freezing in the different experimental groups during the open field test. Values are expressed as mean \pm SEM, n = 10, ***p<0.001 vs. control; a = p<0.001 vs. cooked bean.

Fig 5: Duration of freezing in the different experimental groups during the open field test. Values are expressed as mean \pm SEM, n = 10, *p<0.05 vs. control; a = p<0.05 vs. cooked bean.

Fig 6: Frequency of stretch attends posture in the different experimental groups during the open field test. Values are expressed as mean \pm SEM, n = 10, *p<0.05 vs. control; a = p<0.05 vs. cooked bean.

Fig 7: Frequency of transition in the light/dark transition box test. Values are expressed as mean \pm SEM, n = 10, *p<0.05 vs. control; a = p<0.001 vs. cooked beans.

Discussion

The open field maze (OFM) test provides simultaneous measures of locomotion, exploration and even anxiety (Walsh and Cummins, 1976). Also, the light/dark transition box test is a measure of locomotion and exploration in addition to anxiety.

In the open field test, behaviours such as the number of line crosses and the frequency of rearing are used as measures of locomotor activity, and as a measure of exploration and anxiety. A high frequency of these behaviours (line crossing, rearing) indicates increased locomotion and exploration. In the open field test, the number of lines crossed following chronic consumption of uncooked beans diet was significantly decreased compared to the control. This indicates a lower locomotor and exploratory activity in the uncooked beans group of mice and higher in the control group. The frequency of line crossing in the group of mice that consumed the serotonin precursor diet was also decreased compared to control group. . These observations, shows that beans (uncooked) diet reduced locomotor and exploratory activities in mice. In the light/dark transition box, a similar result, like that of the open field was observed. The line crossing frequencies and that of the frequency of transition of the uncooked beans and serotonin precursor observed groups were significantly lower compared to control. This indicates a lower exploratory and locomotor activity in the uncooked beans and serotonin precursor groups and higher in the control group. This means that locomotor and exploratory activities in the uncooked beans was reduced probably because of serotonin and some yet unknown constituents in beans (uncooked) which have impaired or inhibit other motor areas of the nervous system, notably the motor cortex, cerebellum or spinal cord. The frequency of rearing was not significantly different in the three experimental groups when compared.

It is possible that beans diet may have increased the biosynthesis of serotonin in the brain of the mice which in turn caused the reduced locomotor and exploratory activities.

Conclusion

Our findings therefore suggest that the chronic consumption of uncooked beans diet decreases exploratory and locomotor behaviour.

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